

Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: **Barriers, Solutions** **and Next Steps**

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed poorer health outcomes in marginalized communities, driven by racism and unequal systems. Marginalized communities are groups and populations who are discriminated against or excluded because of unequal power relationships. These communities include racial/ethnic minorities, children, seniors/elderly, low-income, differently-abled, pregnant, incarcerated, and LGBTQ+ persons. Before the pandemic, unfair policies and unequal access to health care centers, clean air and water, and good schools, in the places where marginalized communities live have limited resources for healthy living. Marginalized communities are more likely to work in jobs labeled “essential,” increasing their risk of exposure to COVID-19 and making it more difficult to get time off in order to access testing. The reality during the pandemic is that marginalized communities have experienced a higher risk of getting COVID-19 and dying from it. They have also experienced greater food, housing, and job difficulty. Marginalized communities have fewer community resources, face more obstacles accessing support and services, and have lower access to protection. Community members are well aware of these realities that they have seen through their own lived experience. Lessons and strategies from the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) initiative, funded by the National Institutes of Health (NIH), have helped overcome unfair policies and improve community health. Team members on each RADx-UP project include academics and local community leaders. These partnerships support the use of community-based

testing approaches in marginalized communities to reduce disparities in testing. This policy paper outlines three learning areas:

- Common barriers that prevent fair access to COVID-19 testing
- Policy solutions to increase access to COVID-19 testing and other services
- Ideas to improve responses during COVID-19 or other public health emergencies

At the Start of the Pandemic

Since the start of the pandemic, it has been difficult for marginalized communities to receive COVID-19 testing and other essential medical services. Marginalized communities are overrepresented in essential jobs, such as grocery store clerks and bus drivers, and often lack paid time off and health insurance. Some common challenges include:

- Difficulty accessing testing due to lack of test site locations, limited hours outside of work hours, and insurance requirements
- Early focus on reaching as many people as possible rather than reaching communities experiencing the greatest social vulnerability
- Inconsistent information about how data would be used and who would access it
- Public health messages that were hard to understand and often only available in English

Policy Areas to Advance Equity

The term “policy” refers to regulations, procedures, or actions which an organization or institution uses to achieve a goal. This paper groups the policies and strategies used by RADx-UP projects and community partners to support community testing into five areas (see [Figure 1](#)):

Access: Improved access decreases the obstacles that stop people from going to COVID-19 testing sites, such as the hours, location, and transportation options

Resource Allocation: Successful public health projects give money and supplies to the people who need it most or who may be left out

Data: Trusted data is needed to support leaders and decision-makers as they try to figure out where to send resources and how to create new policies

Communication and Messaging: Successful public health projects include trustworthy, easy to understand communication and should seek to include community voices in messages through authentic partnership.

Payment: Fairer health outcomes are created when those doing health work outside of hospitals are paid.

Three common strategies or **foundational components** are needed for successful community testing. These foundational components are:

Community Engagement: Community engagement recognizes the importance of the voices of communities. When done right, community engagement can help improve health outcomes and trust in healthcare organizations.

Cross-Sector Partnerships: Projects that bring together community members, healthcare professionals, and researchers are more successful than projects that only include one group.

Regulatory Guidance (laws and protocols): Strategies that make things simple, keep health data safe, and reduce paperwork or repeated work help ensure there is a common standard for people and programs.

Figure 1: Policy Framework for Community-Based COVID-19 Testing

WHAT NEXT?

As we continue living with COVID-19 and face new public health challenges, more work needs to be done in the five areas below. RADx-UP academic and community partnerships can use this plan to guide policy conversations.

- Create healthcare services that are easy to access and appreciate the unique culture and voices of different communities
- Collect and share data to help communities develop projects in areas of most need
- Consider current systems and policies that overlook communities most in need of support and resources
- Ensure public health messages are easy to understand and available in multiple languages and formats
- Create fair payment policies that compensate community leaders and organizations for their time and knowledge

These tips from RADx-UP academic and community partners are intended to support policymakers, community organizations and leaders, and health care professionals as they work to make communities healthier through improved policies and access.